

Analysis of the Research on Babur's Heritage

Sevar Ilyasovna Shomurodova

Senior Lecturer, National University of Uzbekistan

Abstract. *The article discusses some aspects of the literary, historical and cultural heritage of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur Kuragoni, a king and poet, a public and statesman, a skilled general. Also, in the assessment of Babur's creativity, the work "Boburnoma" that shines like a diamond "Kuhi Nur" in a gold ring, and how the research and publication of this work is progressing in Uzbekistan and abroad will be given. Differences between original copies of works in manuscripts and ancient books belonging to the heritage of Babur Mirza in other countries are shown, and further work to be done in this regard is shown. The social importance of the decision taken by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to celebrate the 540th anniversary of the birth of the great poet and scientist, famous statesman Zahiriddin Muhammed Babur is emphasized.*

Keywords: *"Boburnoma" - historical-geographic memoir, original copy, Indian Empire, Kashmir, tuyuk, qit'a, ghazal, history of Chigatoy, heritage.*

Introduction: If the list of the greatest representatives of Uzbek literature of the last six centuries begins with the name of Alisher Navoi, then in the second place of this list we will undoubtedly find the name of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. This was noted in due time by Russian, German, Turkish scholars and researchers from other countries who studied Babur's work in the 19th-20th centuries.

In the 2nd issue of the journal "World Literature" for 2013, an article by Tohir Kahhor entitled "Babur's Divan Wanders the World" was published. The article is devoted to a general brief analysis of two books published in Azerbaijan: "Baburnoma" and "Babur's Divan". Tohir Kahhor says: "Babur's Azerbaijani "Selected Works" (Baku, 2011) opens with a preface by R. Askar entitled "The Life, Personality, Works of Ghazi Zahiriddin Babur" (pp. 3-22). It provides detailed information about Babur's life and work. In particular, the comments on the manuscripts of Babur's works in Turkey and Iran are noteworthy. According to the author, several copies of Babur's "Kabul Divan" compiled in 1519 and "Hind Divan" compiled in 1528-29 are kept in various museums. The most complete copy of these divans, which differ greatly from each other, is "Divoni Baburshahi Chigatai" number 3743 in the Istanbul University Library. The 105-page collection contains 119 ghazals and other poems of the poet in various genres, as well as a translation of "Risalai Volidiya". (The second famous copy, number 1230 in the Paris National Library, is 50 pages long, containing 87 ghazals and other poems.) The manuscript number 741 in the Topkapi Palace in Istanbul is 55 pages long. This divan, entitled "Divani Sultanul Babur Mirza Wal Ghufro", contains 111 ghazals and other poems. Therefore, this monument is more valuable than the Paris copy due to its size."

Thanks to this article by Tohir Kahhor, we learned about the great interest in the life and work of Babur in Azerbaijan, where our language and religion are connected. We were aware of the fact that the Turkish Babur scholar Dr. Bilal Yucal published "Divani Babur" based on manuscripts stored in libraries in Turkey, Iran, and Paris, and that the Turkmen scholar Rahimmamat Kuronov also published "Divani Babur" based on this publication.

Main part: The fact that Tohir Kahhor repeated this in his article is a source guide for Babur scholars in Uzbekistan and, in addition to Babur's poetry, it has become both a source of novelty and

a source of fuller enjoyment of Babur's work for every Uzbek. In the "Divan of Babur" there are works on 10 genres of aruz.

In addition to the "Divan", his works are known as "A Treatise on Aruz" (1523-1525), which contains his thoughts on Turkish aruz, "Mubayin" on Islamic law, and "Mubayinul-zakat", which provides information on the tax policy of the 16th century. The latter two works were written in 1521. Babur also translated Khoja Ubaydullah Ahrar Vali's "Walidiya" into Persian in a poetic style.

Speaking about the treasury of Babur's poetic works, we can say that "currently, 119 ghazals, one masnu poem, 209 rubaiyats, more than 10 tyuks and kitai, more than 50 problems, and more than 60 fards have been identified. The composition of the Divan also includes a masnavi with a total volume of 270 verses." The masterpiece of Babur's creative reign is known in our time under the name "Baburnama", but it is a work that he himself sometimes called "Vaqo'e" and sometimes "Tarikh". We think that the change in the name of the work is due to the translators. Because it was written in the Turkic-Chigatai language and was later translated into Persian. According to the custom of that time, memoirs in Persian were named after the author or the king whose biography is being described in the work.

"Baburnama" was written in 1493-1529, and although it describes the events of almost forty years, the history of the XIV-XV-XVI centuries is skillfully intertwined with these descriptions. This work is not only an important source for studying the history of Moverannahr and the territories that were in one way or another connected with Moverannahr, but also provides a lot of valuable information for thinking about the geography, botany and zoology of that period. "Baburnama" has been studied in detail by both our literary critics and historians, as well as foreign scholars, and these studies are ongoing. The Japanese scholar Eiji Mano says about the importance of the work in the study of history: "The main historical sources that we used in studying the history of Chigatai and the Mongols of the XV-XVI centuries are Babur's "Baburnama" and Mirza Muhammad Haidar's "Tarihi Rashidi".

Mirza Muhammad Haidar Duglat (1499 Tashkent - 1551 Kashmir), mentioned by the Japanese Eiji Mano, was Babur's cousin. Babur provided sufficient information about Mirza Muhammad Haidar Duglat in his "Baburnama", while Mirza Muhammad Haidar himself, in his Persian work "Tarihi Rashidi", described in detail the incomparable kindness shown to him by his cousin, the ruler of India, Babur, who was 16 years older than him. The word Haidar means "lion" in Arabic, and Babur means "tiger". The names of the two cousins are similar. By the will of fate, the adventures and wanderings of these two people are also very similar (in order not to deviate from the main topic, we will not dwell on the fate of Mirza Muhammad Haidar Duglat for long).

Mirza Muhammad Haidar began the chapter on Babur in his work "History of the Rashid" as follows:

"Babur the Tsar was born on the sixth day of the month of Muharram in the year 888. One of Ulugbek's famous scholars, Mawlana Munir Marginani, found the date of his birth to be "Shashi Muharram" (this is 888 AH in the abjad calendar, i.e. 1483 AD (note ours)). Hazrat Eshan Khoja Abdullah Quddisa Sirrahu was asked to name the baby. He blessed the child with the name Zahiriddin Muhammad." "History of the Rashid", which was written using "Baburnama" as a reference, was eventually evaluated by historians as "the only complete work on Central Asia."

The fact that the original copy of "Baburnama" is kept in the British Museum in London under the number OR3714, a copy copied in 1598 in the National Museum of India in New Delhi, and 69 miniatures in the Museum of Oriental Culture in Moscow once again emphasizes the historical significance of this work. Among historical works such as Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnoma", Fazlullo Rashiddin's "Jami' ut-tavorikh", Hamidullo Mustafa's "Tarihi Guzide", Atamalik Juvaini's "Tarihi Jahonkushoy", Hafiz Tanish Bukhari's "Abdullanoma", Muhammad Salih's "Shaybaniynoma", Aliakbar Dekhudo's "Lugatnoma Dekhudo", Mirza Muhammad Haidar's "Tarihi Rashidi" provides remarkable information about the geography, history, politics, behavior of historical figures, and the life of ordinary people of Transoxiana and present-day Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, northwestern India, and southern China in the 15th-16th centuries. In addition to information about the history, politics, historical figures, geography, and lifestyle of ordinary people

of the 15th-16th centuries, "Baburnoma" also provides information about the animals of this period and place ("Baburnoma", chapter 18), plants ("Baburnoma", Chapter 19), birds and beasts ("Boburnoma", Chapter 20), climate ("Boburnoma", Chapter 21), hydrography ("Boburnoma", Chapter 22), attitude to natural resources ("Boburnoma", Chapter 23). Babur's work glorifies actions that symbolize humanity, kindness, and goodness in general.

Conclusion: This is once again confirmed by the Resolution of the President of our republic on "Celebrating the 540th Anniversary of the Birth of Babur", adopted on January 25, 2023. This Resolution, along with emphasizing the cultural, historical, social, and state significance of Babur's activities, emphasizes the need to further develop and accelerate work on studying Babur's heritage. The Resolution also states the need to create a translation of "Boburnoma" and other works of Babur into the modern Uzbek language. In our opinion, this is a wise move aimed at raising the cultural level and potential of the future generation. The directive in the resolution, "...to establish a scholarship named after Babur for students of higher education institutions studying history and geography," officially reinforces our idea that the "Baburnoma" we mentioned at the beginning of our article will also be of great help in the study of geography.

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